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USE OF MUSICAL GAME TECHNOLOGY IN MUSIC LESSONS

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Annotation: *Game methods are a variety of student activities in the form of exercises, as well as laboratory and practical work. These methods can serve to acquire new knowledge and consolidate previously acquired knowledge, but their main task is to teach students to apply the acquired knowledge in practice in different contexts and to develop skills and competencies in students.*

Key words: *game technology, game method, sing, dance, vocal skills.*

Games should be a key tool in the physical education of school-age children. With the help of games, children learn useful actions that are necessary for them and practice them constantly.

Moving games are more appealing to children because they have great potential to apply the knowledge and skills needed to solve a task that requires precise movement in a changing game movement.

In the process of active games, especially games with signs of competition, children develop and improve such qualities as strength, agility, dexterity, endurance.

Games help children develop the ability to adapt their actions to the actions of their peers, to subordinate personal interests to the interests of the community, to cultivate patience, self-control, and a sense of responsibility for class or group success.

Obligation to follow the rules of active play disciplines children, nurtures their will. The need to firmly choose what style of action to achieve the goal of the game requires the demonstration of independence, the display of personal qualities such as diligence.

Many action games are educational in nature and involve imitating different animals and birds, repeating real human movements.

Moving games have great opportunities for the teacher to interact with the children. The teacher explains the content of the game and its rules. Children learn the meaning of new words. Word-of-mouth, talking, and singing games also help to stimulate communication.

Singing and dancing games are often based on folk songs and dances to help children develop qualities such as great emotion. The ratio of different types of games varies depending on the different qualities.

The school uses a play method to teach children to move. Game techniques are used in elementary school to teach movement. There are games based on children's imitation of various animal movements and human behavior: children fly like birds, row like donkeys, jump like rabbits, and so on. Such imitative actions give the lessons a high spirit. Children diligently perform actions that have a common meaning: they fly in a supposed plane, travel by train, and play similar games willingly. The high spirits of such games attract children with great interest.

Animated games can be played every day outside of class, during outings. Particular attention should be paid to the fact that children are more active in these games. The content of the games should be relevant to the children's pre-game and post-game activities. After classes such as drawing and math, it is recommended to play action games. After music and physical education classes, it is advisable to hold games with moderate movement.

It is very important to intensify and correct children's interactions. As a result of the music teacher's attentive approach to the children, skillfully reminding them in a timely manner that they should play together, and emphasizing that the children should help each other or be supportive of each other, In the middle, a good friendly relationship is formed.

Game methods are used to develop students' vocal and choral skills, to analyze the structure and means of expression of music, to identify its genres and forms, and to develop the skills and abilities to study note writing. For example, in the development of vocal-choral skills, in the study of note-taking or stepping into music, the method of exercises is mainly used, which is used in various types of activities.

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